

A NOTE ON A METHOD OF ERDŐS AND THE STANLEY-ELDER THEOREMS

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Abstract

An enumeration method of Erdős is applied to provide a generalization of the theorems of Stanley and Elder on integer partitions.

1. Introduction

In [4], Erdős proved the asymptotics of the partition function $p(n)$ by elementary means. His starting point was the identity of Ford [7] (probably going back to Euler):

$$np(n) = \sum_{j=1}^n p(n-j)\sigma(j), \quad (1)$$

where $\sigma(j)$ is the sum of divisors of j . The standard proof of (1) is by logarithmic differentiation of

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} p(n)q^n = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-q^n} \quad (2)$$

([7], also [1, p.98]). However, Erdős wanted to avoid even this amount of analysis. So he rewrote (1) as follows

$$np(n) = \sum_{v \geq 1} \sum_{k \geq 1} vp(n-kv), \quad (3)$$

and then he remarked: “We easily obtain (3) by adding up all the partitions of n , and noting that v occurs in $p(n-v)$ partitions.” We assume he is telegraphing that v appears twice in $p(n-2v)$ partitions, etc.

This same counting method makes transparent a very general theorem in partitions.

Definition 1. A *partition configuration*, A , is a non-decreasing sequence of non-negative integers (a_1, \dots, a_k) with *length* k and weight $w(A) = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_k$.

Definition 2. A partition, $\lambda : \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 + \dots + \lambda_m$ ($1 \leq \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_m$) is said to have a partition configuration A if there is a subset of parts of λ of the form $a_1 + j, a_2 + j, \dots, a_k + j$ for some $j \geq 1$.

For example, the partition $(2 + 4 + 4 + 5 + 8 + 9)$ contains an instance of $A = (0, 3, 6, 7)$ because the parts $2, 5, 8, 9$ exceed by 2 the successive entries of A .

Theorem 1. Given a partition configuration A , in each partition of n we count the number of distinct configurations A and then sum over all partitions of n . Call this sum $p_A(n)$. Then

$$p_A(n) = p(k; n - w(A)), \tag{4}$$

where $p(k; n)$ is the total number of appearances of k in the partitions of n .

As an example of Theorem 1, we take $A = (0, 1, 2)$ (having length $k = 3$ and weight $w(A) = 3$) and $n = 10$. The partitions of 10 containing the partition configuration A are $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 3$, $1 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 2 + 3$, $1 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 3$, $1 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 3$ and $1 + 2 + 3 + 4$ which contain A $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 2 = 6$ times. So $p_A(10) = 6$. As for $p(3; 10 - 3) = p(3; 7)$ we see that the partitions of 7 containing 3 's are $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 3$, $1 + 1 + 2 + 3$, $2 + 2 + 3$, $1 + 3 + 3$, $3 + 4$. So $p(3; 7) = 1 + 1 + 1 + 2 + 1 = 6$, the total number of 3 's in the partitions of 7 .

In Section 2, we use the Erdős method to provide a short proof of Theorem 1 together with the theorems of Elder and Stanley (see Corollaries 2 and 3). We refer the reader to [8] for an extensive account of the Elder and Stanley theorems. In Section 3, we extend these ideas to a question concerning divisibility restrictions on parts. We conclude with some general observations.

2. Proof of Theorem 1

We remark, following Erdős, that to obtain $p_A(n)$ there must be $p(n - ((a_1 + j) + \dots + (a_k + j)))$ partitions which contain the partition configuration A in the form $(a_1 + j) + (a_2 + j) + \dots + (a_k + j)$.

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n \geq 0} p_A(n)q^n &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{(j+a_1)+(j+a_2)+\dots+(j+a_k)}}{\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)} = \frac{q^{w(A)} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} q^{kj}}{\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)} \\
 &= \frac{q^{w(A)+k}}{(1 - q^k)^2 \prod_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq k}}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)} \tag{5} \\
 &= q^{w(A)} (q^k + 2q^{2k} + 3q^{3k} + \dots) \prod_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq k}}^{\infty} (1 + q^n + q^{2n} + q^{3n} + \dots) \\
 &= q^{w(A)} \sum_{n \geq 0} p(k, n)q^n,
 \end{aligned}$$

and Theorem 1 follows by comparing coefficients of q^n in the extremes of (5). \square

Corollary 1 (Stanley’s Theorem [2],[8]). *The number of 1’s in the partitions of n is equal to the number of parts that appear at least once in a given partition of n , summed over all partitions of n .*

Proof. Take $A = (0)$ in Theorem 1. \square

A more general theorem is attributed to Paul Elder.

Corollary 2 (Elder’s Theorem [2][8]). *The number of j ’s appearing in the partitions of n is equal to the number of parts that appear at least j times in a given partition of n , summed over all partitions of n .*

Proof. Take $A = (0, 0, \dots, 0)$ of length j in Theorem 1. \square

Corollary 3. *In each partition of n count the number of sequences of consecutive integers of length k . Then sum these numbers over all partitions of n . This equals the number of appearances of k in the partitions of $n - k(k - 1)/2$.*

This result is originally due to Knopfmacher and Munagi and occurs as Theorem 5 in [9].

Proof. In Theorem 1 take $A = (0, 1, \dots, k - 1)$. \square

3. Divisibility of Parts

The method of Erdős can be further extended in many ways.

Theorem 2. *Given $k \geq 1$, in each partition of n we count the number of times a part divisible by k appears uniquely (i.e., is not a repeated part); then sum these numbers over all the partitions of n . The result is equal to the number of appearances of $2k$ in the partitions of $n + k$.*

Example. $k = 1, n = 5$. There are eight singletons in the partitions of 5: $5, 4 + 1, 3 + 2, 3 + 1 + 1, 2 + 2 + 1, 2 + 1 + 1 + 1, 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$. There are eight 2's in the partitions of 6: $4 + 2, 3 + 2 + 1, 2 + 2 + 2, 2 + 2 + 1 + 1, 2 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 1$.

Remark. The case $k = 1$ was published as a problem in [3].

Proof. The generating function for multiples of k being unique parts is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{q^{kj}}{\prod_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq kj}}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)} &= \frac{1}{\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)} \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} q^{kj} (1 - q^{kj}) \\ &= \frac{1}{\prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - q^n)} \left(\frac{q^k}{1 - q^k} - \frac{q^{2k}}{1 - q^{2k}} \right) \\ &= \frac{q^k}{(1 - q^{2k})} \cdot \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - q^n)} \\ &= q^{-k} (q^{2k} + 2q^{2 \cdot 2k} + 3q^{3 \cdot 2k} + \dots) \prod_{\substack{n=1 \\ n \neq 2k}}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1 - q^n}, \end{aligned}$$

and this last expression is the generating function for the number of appearances of $2k$ in the partitions of $n + k$. □

4. Conclusion

It is clear that the scope of Theorem 1 could be generalized to account for results like Theorem 5. We should also note that Dastidar and Gupta [2] have generalized the Stanley and Elder theorems where they add what they term "packets" of size k to partitions, and this count equals the number of appearances of k in the partitions of $n + k$.

Finally, we note the charming survey "A Fine Rediscovery" by R. Gilbert [8], which provides a detailed history of the Stanley and Elder theorems and points out that N. J. Fine was the original discoverer of both theorems [5],[6].

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